

Different Interpretations of $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \hbar/2$?

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We have argued in a previous note (1) that one may obtain the p-x uncertainty relationship in a mathematical manner. This math approach may also be applied to E and t we argue. In this note, we try to establish the interpretation of these uncertainty relationships. We argue that for a given $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$, i.e. each x point has the same weight, but this is not the full picture because there is a resolution in x, namely \hbar/p , under the surface so to speak. Given $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, an impulse hit is with a specific $\exp(ipx)$, yet $W^*(x)W(x)$ yields an x distribution. This distribution is a consequence of the interference of different $\exp(ipx)$ resolution profiles in x as well as a very important condition, namely: $-\hbar \hbar/2m \ d/dx \ d/x \ W + V(x) W = E_n W$. This condition introduces Newtonian energy conservation on average and uses the $\exp(ipx)$ resolution profiles in x to build an x distribution which may have different heights. We argue that although crests and troughs are linked to average resolution profiles in x, (a quantum effect), different heights of W (real) indicate that more time is spent in one x region than another (a classical effect).

We consider $W(x,t) = \sum \text{over } E_n \ a(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W(E_n, x)$ for two energy levels and choose an $x=x_i$ so that $\cos((E_1-E_0)t)$ remains. We note that one may choose a time range of $(0, T)$ where $T = 2\pi / (E_1 - E_0)$. For a given x_i , orthogonality of $\exp(-iE_0 t)$ and $\exp(-iE_1 t)$ on $(0, T)$ allow one to use the uncertainty relation form: $\sqrt{\text{Var}(E, x_i) \text{Var}(t, x_i)} \geq \hbar/2$. In such a case, $\text{Var}(t, x_i)$ contains a classical type piece and a quantum one.

It seems that in the literature (2), however, the uncertainty relationship is linked to the order of measurement and (2) provides a different approach to dealing with the energy-time uncertainty relationship which we briefly mention.

Math Approach to Creating an Uncertainty Relationship

In (1) we presented a math approach to finding an uncertainty relation for x-p. We noted that $\exp(ipx)$ is the dynamic probability for a particle with momentum p, but argued that each x point should represent the same weight, i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. This result should hold for any p. To show that this is the case, we noted that:

$$d/dx (x \exp(ipx)) - x \ d/dx \exp(ipx) = 1 \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

We argued that the 1 on the RHS indicates that $x \rightarrow x+dx$ for all p. Thus, if one writes: $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$, then:

$$\int dx \ W^*(x) \{ d/dx (xW) - x dW/dx \} = 1 \quad ((2))$$

We used ((2)) together with a quadratic polynomial with one real root to write the x-p uncertainty relationship- see (1).

The point we wish to make is that one may apply the same math to $\exp(-iEt)$ with $W(x,t) = \sum_{n} a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$. In particular, one may choose $x=x_1$ and treat $W_n(x_1)$ as real numerical weights combined with $a_n(E_n)$. This then leads to an uncertainty relationship at each x_1 , namely:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(E, x_1) \text{Var}(t, x_1)} \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((3))$$

The question then becomes one of interpretation, we argue. One issue that arises immediately is that $W(x)$ satisfies boundary conditions at $x=\pm\infty$, i.e. $W(x)=0$ at these points. For $W(x,t)$, one may have periodicity and so one needs to choose a time range such that various $\exp(-iE_n t)$ are orthogonal. Later, we try to show that this can be done for a two state system by using $T = 2\pi\hbar/(E_1 - E_0)$.

Interpretation of the x-p Uncertainty Relation

We note that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a resolution in space linked with $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$, but that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. If one creates:

$$W(x) = \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

one notices that not only is a different weight given to each p , but that $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents a set of crests with different widths and heights. One may ask: How specifically are the $a(p)$ values obtained? They follow from forcing an average conservation of energy on $W(x)$. We note that $W(x)$ involves interference. Thus:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W + V(x) W = E_n W_n \quad ((5))$$

The point we wish to make is that classical ideas enter on average through ((5)). In particular, if a crest or trough of $W(x)$ is higher than another, then this seems to indicate that the particle spends more time in the x region of the higher $W(x)$ value. The shape of the crest (e.g. its width), however, is linked to x -resolutions which is a quantum effect, albeit this resolution is linked to ((5)) which treats averages as classical. The $\text{Var}(p)$ has the sense of a momentum distribution, but the probability is $a(p)^2$ is chosen in a manner which is linked to ((4)) and ((5)). If there are several crests and troughs in $W(x)$, as in the case of a quantum oscillator, having one standard deviation for all loses quite a bit of information.

It seems that there is a variance for each crest of $W^*(x)W(x)$, but this would involve position $x=0$ in the center of each crest. One global variance gives a sense of the range of the particle, but it is biased by speed, e.g. a low speed at a peak of $W^*(x)W(x)$ means a high peak and vice versa. For example, for an oscillator, there is a high speed at $x=0$ and so little contribution to $\text{Var}(x)$ from this region, whereas speed becomes low at the classical turning points meaning there is not only an x of the length of roughly the classical amplitude, but also a high peak value.

The ground state is perhaps the best for seeing quantum effects because there is no enhanced height from endpoints for $n>0$ states of an oscillator. Here one sees the x variance associated with average resolution needed to satisfy ((5)) for the lowest possible energy. Thus

this quantum resolution is still linked to a classical average type equation, namely ((5)). One might argue that $\text{Var}(x)$ for the quantum oscillator ground state is not so much a case of a particle spending time at high values of $W^*(x)W(x)$, but rather a case of resolution of x issues. If one cannot resolve the exact position of a particle then one cannot really follow it in time within this region. Higher energy levels, however, do bring in the idea of a classical lingering time as higher peaks mean a lower rms speed and a longer lingering time which affects $\text{Var}(x)$. Thus, it is difficult to separate the quantum resolution features of $\text{Var}(x)$ from the classical lingering time effects for states higher than the ground state. We argue that $\text{Var}(x)$ is not completely a quantum result. Furthermore, one global x gives a variance which washes out the various crests of $W^*(x)W(x)$ for states above the ground state. As mentioned, there is a variance for each of these crests. These give uncertainty in x as a function of x , not a single number that is used in the x - p Heisenberg uncertainty relation. There is, however, no Heisenberg uncertainty relation for these variances by themselves.

Classical Versus Quantum x -Variance

$\text{Var}(x)$, as noted above, is not a purely quantum feature. For example, for the ground state of a quantum oscillator, one may compute:

$$\text{Var}(x) = \int dx x^2 W_0 W_0 \quad \text{where } W_0 = N \exp(-.5\sqrt{km} x^2) \quad \text{where } N \text{ is a normalization constant} \quad ((6))$$

There is also a classical variance because the quantum one contains lingering times. One may use $P(x)=C/v(x)$ where C is a normalization constant and $.5mv(x)v(x) + .5kx^2 = h \sqrt{k/m}$ (.5). ((7))Then:

$$\text{Var}(x) \text{ classical} = \int dx C/v(x). \quad ((8))$$

The quantum ground state $\text{Var}(x)$ is not 0, but neither is the corresponding classical $\text{Var}(x)$. A difference is that classically a particle may be at rest at $x=0$ and in this case, $\text{Var}(x) \text{ classical}=0$. If h , Planck's constant, is considered to be almost 0, then ((7)) has an energy of 0 and $v(x)=0$ and $x=0$ so $\text{Var}(x) \text{ classical}$ is essentially 0.

Importance of Boundary Conditions on $W(x)$ and $\text{Var}(x)$

One may notice that bound states $W(x)$ tend to 0 at $x=\pm$ infinite and this prevents the global $\text{Var}(x)$ from being too large. Thus, the single particle is localized within a region of space although $\text{Var}(x)$ does not represent pure quantum mechanical length uncertainty. The case of the variance of t (time) is trickier because one may need to restrict the time interval, but must ensure that $\exp(-iEnt)$ s are orthogonal on this interval.

An Interpretation of a Time--Energy Uncertainty Relation at xi

In the case of time dependency, one might consider the following:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_{\text{over } E_n} a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((6))$$

One problem with ((6)) is that it does not vanish at large t. Rather for two energy levels:

$$W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = a_1 a_1 W_1 W_1 + a_0 a_0 W_0 W_0 + a_1 a_0 W_1 W_0 2 \cos[(E_1 - E_0)t] \quad ((7))$$

There are actually two time effects in ((6)) because one has $\exp(-iE_n t)$ associated with quantum time resolution and peak values of $W_n(x)$'s, associated with v_{rms} , i.e. lingering times around each crest $W^*_n(x)W_n(x)$ for each n.

For $t=0$, one has a superposition of $W_n(x)$'s which are a set of crests and troughs for an oscillator. Thus, one might expect an average $W(x,t=0)$ with a set of crests and troughs with different heights and widths. The different heights are associated with an average of a set of v_{rms} values and represent some kind of averaged lingerin time for each peak of $W^*(x, t=0)W(x,t=0)$.

A key task is to find a finite time period such that $\exp(-iE_0 t)$ and $\exp(-iE_1 t)$ are orthogonal. This is needed to establish the E-t uncertainty relationship in the first place. We choose a specific x point in ((7)) in order to retain $\cos((E_1 - E_0) t)$ which would be lost due to $\int dx W_1 W_0 = 0$.

The time period needed is: $\int_0^T \exp(-i(E_1 - E_0)t) dt = 0$ so $T = 2 * 3.14 / (E_1 - E_0)$ ((8))

Then, one may calculate a $\text{Var}(E)$ and $\text{Var}(t)$ for a particular $x=x_1$ in ((7)). This should satisfy the usual Heisenberg uncertainty relation form $\text{Var}(E, x_1) \text{Var}(t, x_1) \geq \hbar/2$. One may see that the first two terms in ((7)) (RHS) are constants and so are linked to a usual classical type variance of t, but the third term is not. It is a quantum term which shows interference in time. One may choose arbitrary values for $a_0 a_0$ and $a_1 a_1$ such that $a_0 a_0 + a_1 a_1 = 1$.

Different Interpretation of A Time -Energy Uncertainty Relation

In (2) a very different approach is taken for a time-energy type uncertainty relation. The identity: $\sqrt{\text{Var}(A)\text{Var}(B)} \geq \frac{1}{2} | \langle i [A, B] \rangle |$ ((9)) is used, where A and B are operators and [] means commutation. An operator A is chosen representing an observable which changes in time, for example a piece of time dependent potential (added to a usual $V(x)$). Then:

$$dA/dt = 1/i\hbar [A, H] \quad ((10))$$

One may use ((9)) for A and H: $\sqrt{\text{Var}(H) \text{Var}(A)} \geq \frac{i}{2} \langle [A, H] \rangle = \hbar/2 \langle dA/dt \rangle$ ((11))

It is argued in (2) that to notice a change in A, it should be \geq than $\sqrt{\text{Var}(A)}$, so

$$\Delta t \geq \sqrt{\text{Var}(A)} / |\langle dA/dt \rangle| \quad ((12))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, mathematically one may create the same type of uncertainty relation for both x - p and E - t by using the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ s and $\exp(-iEnt)$. (In the case of time, this may mean choosing a special $(0, T)$ interval.) As shown in (1) one may obtain a mathematical $\sqrt{\text{Var}(x)\text{Var}(p)} \geq \hbar/2$. We argue that a similar result holds mathematically for E and t , but in this case one does not have $W(x) \rightarrow 0$ as $x \rightarrow$ infinite. In the case of a two energy level system, one has oscillatory behavior and may choose $T = 2\pi\hbar/(E_1 - E_0)$ as the upper bound of time when calculating a variance. We note that in both the $\text{Var}(x)$ case and $\text{Var}(t)$ case, there are both classical and quantum effects in $\text{Var}(x)$ and $\text{Var}(t)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Heisenberg x - p Uncertainty Relation As a Statement of Spatial Invariance? (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
2. Rais, J. and van Hees, H. and Greiner, C. Bound State Formation in Time Dependent Potentials (2022) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2207.04898>